

Polarized intensity (mJy beam^{-1})

0.30

0.35

53°49'00" 08

$z_{\text{Sp}}=1.197$

48'30"

00"

47'30"

100 kpc

16^h06^m09^s 06^s 03^s 00^s

RA (J2000)

Dec (J2000)

